

Effects of Labless Kits On Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Physics in Osun State

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Abstract

This study examined the effects of Labless kits on senior secondary school students' academic performance in Physics in Osun state. Specifically, the research determined which of Labless kits and conventional laboratory would provide better academic performance in Physics. The study adopted the quasi- experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The sample consisted of 206 students drawn from six public secondary schools in Osun State. The selection of the sample was done using multistage sampling technique. Two Senatorial districts were randomly selected from the three senatorial districts in Osun. Three Local Governments were randomly selected from each of the two senatorial districts earlier selected, making a total of six Local governments selected. One public secondary school was randomly selected from each of the six local governments chosen for the study. An intact class from each of the six selected schools was used for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used to assign the schools into labless kits and laboratory groups respectively. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was developed, validated and used to generate the data for the study. The research question raised was answered descriptively while the three hypotheses generated were tested using t- test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The result of the study showed that the use of labless kits produced better students' academic performance in Physics than using conventional laboratory. The use of labless kits helped the students to achieve maximally in Physics during teaching as this was revealed in their performance. Based on

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the findings, the use of Labless kits should be encouraged in the teaching of Physics in secondary schools. Physics teachers should be given adequate orientation through workshops and seminars to update their knowledge in the use of Labless kits strategy in teaching.

Keywords: Labless kits, practical skill, academic performance,

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Introduction

Physics as a science subject is the study of physical properties of matter and its interaction with energy. It is characteristically an experimental subject; concepts and principles generated from Physics are very useful in understanding of natural phenomena in sciences. This implies that effective practical activities in Physics are significant because they allow learners to form a bridge between what they hear, see, handle (hands-on) and scientific ideas that account for their observations (brains-on). Physics is one of the science subjects studied at the senior secondary education level as it lays foundation for further study in Physics related course at higher levels such as medicine, nursing, pharmacy, food technology and others. Physics is a subject that requires a lot of practical work using physics laboratory equipment.

Despite the importance of this subject, it seems that the teaching and learning of Physics has been fraught with challenges such as low academic performance in secondary schools. Remarkable among the causes for students' low academic performance in Physics in school include: poorly equipped Physics laboratories, poor Science and Mathematics background of students at the junior secondary level of education, inadequate motivation of teachers, inappropriate teaching strategies employed by the teachers, poor remuneration and insufficient number of qualified Physics teachers (NERDC, 2009; Jegede & Adedayo, 2013). These factors have similarly added to deterioration in performance of students' performance in Physics at the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (SSCE).

The underachievement in science; particularly in Physics is worrying to the educationists, governments and science educators, because of the fact that it is at the secondary education level that a sound foundation for further study in science and science related disciplines is laid. All-encompassing Physics education therefore is unavoidable in order to produce the desired scientists needed for the scientific advancement of this country. Physics is a practical oriented subject that requires a lot of practical work using physics laboratory equipment. Physics laboratory equipment must not only be adequately provided in schools but must be optimally utilized for its effective teaching (by teachers) and meaningful learning (by students) (Lawal, 2006).

There are many teaching strategies that could be used in familiarizing the students with practical works so as to improve their academic performance but the two strategies this research is interested in are labless kits and conventional laboratory. Researchers through the advancement in technology were able to make use of an innovative labless kits or ready-to-use kits as alternative to the conventional laboratory. The labless kits (microscience kits) practical apparatuses were produced and comprised pre-selected collection of scientific apparatus designed to illustrate particular scientific principles, usually linked to curriculum material. They are also affordable and far cheaper than conventional laboratory apparatuses and materials, (UNESCO, 2013).

The first large scale labless kits were produced in 1992 by the Research and Development in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education (RADMASTE) Centre at the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg (South Africa). They are small, virtually unbreakable and inexpensive, and have been designed to enhance the quality, relevance and accessibility of science and technology education, and also to involve the learner in applying scientific knowledge to real life situation (Rachmanwati, 2013). These labless kits have been produced and introduced on a large scale to more than 80 countries including Nigeria, South Africa, Cameroon, Kenya, Ethiopia, Sudan, Tanzania, Gambia among others. This was achieved

by introductory workshops for local educators and initiation of pilot projects. The general overall objectives of this project are to:

1. promote practical science experimentation using labless kits as an advocacy tools amongst policy makers
2. improve science curricula by inclusion of hands-on experimentation for a better understanding of science
3. increase the interest of young people in science so as to promote gender equality, scientific literacy and choice of a scientific career, (UNESCO, 2013).

Ready-to-use kits, also known as Labless Kits are to provide science teachers with an empowering tool to help them increase learners' motivation, curiosity, interest, thinking skills and understanding. The Labless Kits were designed to enable experiments to be performed without the need for laboratory facilities, electricity or running water and demonstrations can be performed anywhere, even outdoors. According to Science Demo Limited. The characteristics of Ready-to-use experiments or labless lab include:

1. creation of an exciting phenomenon within minutes, leading to an inquiry guidelines and background information, (including questions and answers for teachers) and video manuals
2. most kits are re-usable
3. refills are available
4. kits are easy to use and safe
5. kits are modular and can fit all science curricula
6. kits can be used anywhere
7. No running water or electricity is needed.

Therefore, the focus of this study is to consider the effects of Labless kits on senior secondary school students' academic performance in Physics in Osun state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the effects of labless kits on senior secondary school students' academic performance in Physics in Osun state. Specifically, the research find out which of labless kits and conventional laboratory will provide better achievement of students in Physics.

Researcher Question

1. What are the effects of labless kits on the achievement of students in Physics?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study.

1. There is no significant difference between the pre-test mean score of students exposed to Labless kits and those taught with conventional laboratory.
2. There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean score of students exposed to Labless kits and those taught with conventional laboratory.
3. There is no significant difference between the post-test mean score of students exposed to Labless kits and those exposed to conventional laboratory.

Methodology

This study adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design (one experimental group and control group).

The paradigm for the design is as shown below.

O₁ X O₂: Experimental group
O₃ C O₄: Control group

Where:

O₁, O₃= Pre-test

O₂, O₄= Post-test

X – Treatment via Labless Kits

C – Treatment via Conventional laboratory

The independent variables were the use of Labless kits and conventional laboratory. The dependent variable was the academic performance. The targeted population for the study was the 57,109 Senior Secondary Schools (S.S.S.) two students in public secondary schools in Osun State. The sample consisted of 206 students drawn from six public secondary schools in Osun State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was used to collect relevant data for this study. PAT was self-designed by the researcher. It consisted of two sections; A and B, section A consisted of bio-data of the respondents which include the name of the school, and sex. Section B comprised of 30 objectives items with four options. The items covered all the topics taught for six weeks. The instrument was used as both pre-test and post-test. The content of PAT used for pre-test was reshuffled for the post-test in order to prevent practice effect.

The Physics Achievement Test (PAT) was given to experienced senior secondary school Physics teachers and Tests and Measurement experts. The face and content validity were ensured by assessing the wordings and ambiguity of the test items as well as their coverage. The final draft of the instrument was done based on the corrections and suggestions made by the experts. The reliability of PAT was carried out by administering the instrument on 25 participants in one of the school outside the sampled area using test-retest method. They were of comparable age with the participants in this study. After a period of two weeks, the instrument was re-administered on the same participants. The data collected were collated and analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis, which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.89. This value was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable for use in this study.

Before carrying out the research in the schools, the researcher obtained permission from the authorities of the six schools to carry out the experiment in the schools. Afterwards, a day workshop was organized for the research assistants on the respective methods used in teaching their students from the selected schools. The treatment was carried out in three stages:

Stage I: Pre Treatment Stage: The researcher carried out the pre-test before introducing the treatment for each group. The answer sheets were collected and graded with the marking guide. The performance of the students was recorded for analysis.

Stage II: Treatment Stage:

- a) Experimental Group (Labless Kits): Labless Kits were used for teaching of the five topics in Physics namely: The Bernoulli effect – Pressure in an air stream, visualizing the concept of pressure, floating bodies in liquids of different densities, attractive force between particles in solid, and the effect of heat on a bi – metallic strip. Students were exposed to eighty minutes of experimental work and discussion for six consecutive weeks by the research assistants.
- b) Control Group: The control group has no special treatment, they were taught with the Conventional laboratory within the period of six weeks by research assistants.

Stage III: Post Treatment Stage: Post-test was carried out immediately after the treatment to each group with the same time duration as observed during the pre- test. The same Physics Achievement Test questions used during the pre-test was re-arranged to avoid practice effect and administered to the experimental group and control group.

The question raised was answered using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, mean, standard deviation and bar-chart. All the hypotheses generated for the study were analyzed using inferential statistics of t-test and analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA). All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The research question raised was subjected to descriptive analysis using mean scores.

Question 1: What are the effects of labless kits on the achievement of students in Physics?

The pre-test and post-test scores of students in the two groups were used to answer this question.

Table 1: Mean scores of students exposed to labless kits and conventional laboratory

Groups	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Labless Kits	Pre Test	97	8.71	0.71	15.57
	Post Test		24.28	0.92	
Conventional Laboratory	Pre Test	109	8.59	0.81	6.96
	Post Test		15.55	0.97	
Total		206			

Table 1 shows that the mean difference in students' performance in Physics between pre-test and post-test scores for labless kits is 15.57, and conventional laboratory is 6.96. It appears that the use of labless kits and conventional laboratory influences students' performance in Physics with the use of labless kits being the more effective in the teaching of Physics. Figure 1 further shows the pre-test and post-test scores of students in the two groups.

Figure 1: Pre-test and post-test scores of students exposed to labless kits and conventional laboratory

Figure 1 shows that the difference in students' performance between pre-test and post-test scores for Labless is more than Conventional laboratory. The obvious differences show that the use of Labless kits is more effective than conventional laboratory.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of students exposed to labless kits and those taught with conventional laboratory.

Table 2: t-test analysis for Pre – test Mean Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Groups

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P (Sig)	Remark
Labless Kits	97	8.71	0.71	204	1.17	0.244	Not Significant
Conventional	109	8.59	0.81				

P>0.05

Table 2 shows that the t-cal value of 1.17 is not significant because the P value (0.244) > 0.05 level of significance, this implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the pre-test mean score of students exposed to labless kits and conventional laboratory. This implies that the two groups were homogenous at the commencement of this study

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean score of students exposed to Labless kits and those taught with conventional laboratory.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Pre – test and Post – test Mean Scores of Students under the Groups

Sources	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3909.864 ^a	2	1954.932	2176.320*	.000
Covariate	606.368	1	606.368	675.037*	.000
Groups	3880.451	1	3880.451	4319.897*	.000
Error	182.350	203	.898		
Total	83716.000	206			
Corrected Total	4092.214	205			

R Squared = .955 (Adjusted R Squared = .955)

* P < 0.05

Table 3 shows that there is a significant difference in the pre – test and post – test mean scores of students in the groups (Labless kits and conventional laboratory) as P(.000)<0.05 and F-calculated (1, 204) = 4319.897 is greater than F-table (3.00) at 0.05 level of significance. This result led to the rejection of the hypothesis. Hence, there is significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean score of students exposed to Labless kits and conventional laboratory. The use of Labless kits and conventional laboratory are effective and influences students' performance in Physics.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students exposed to Labless kits and conventional laboratory.

Table 4: t-test analysis for Post – test Mean Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Groups

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P (Sig)	Remark
Labless	97	24.28	0.92	204	66.12*	0.00	Significant
Conventional	109	15.55	0.97				

*P<0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 66.12 is significant because the P value (0.00) < 0.05 level of significance, this implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students exposed to Labless and conventional laboratory. The mean scores show a large difference in favour of Labless kits.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that the use of Labless kits and conventional laboratory both influence students' performance in Physics but using Labless kits produced a better effect. This finding agrees with that of Awotua, Williams and Aderonmu (2015) that the use of Labless kits would lead to good performance in Physics. The importance of Labless kits is especially apparent in developing the skills, interest and attitudes of the students in an interaction with the materials and the teacher. It is obvious from the findings that Labless kits is fundamental to a good performance in Physics. This is so because the equipment enables the students to grow independently without restrictions to rigid procedures in textbook and syllabuses.

Furthermore, results showed significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of students in Physics among the groups especially those exposed to Labless kits. This result agrees with the submission of Ogunleye and Adepeju (2011), Lasisi (2008) and Asiyai (2012) and Moeller, Theiler & Wu (2012) that exposing students to Labless kits will lead to a better performance in Physics. The probable reason for the large difference might be due to the fact that Labless kits are student centred which allow students to interact with each other, the materials and the teacher as well as to enquire, search, compare and generalize without undue intrusion or direction from the teacher who only fosters learning.

Findings of the study also revealed that a significant difference exists in the post – test mean scores of students exposed to Labless kits and conventional laboratory, with students exposed to Labless kits performing better than those exposed to the conventional laboratory. This agreed with the submission of Seweje (2010) that good teaching strategies have the potent of improving cognition of students. This also justifies the earlier postulate of this study that Labless kits could facilitate meaningful learning of Physics.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that the use of labless kits produced better students' academic performance in Physics than using conventional laboratory. The use of labless kits helped the students to achieve maximally in Physics during teaching as this was revealed in their performance. It is therefore recommended that the use of Labless kits should be encouraged in the teaching of Physics in secondary schools. Also, Physics teachers should be given adequate orientation through workshops and seminars to update their knowledge in the use of Labless kits in teaching.

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